

Microspherules, meltglass, and nanoparticle evidence from the Younger Dryas boundary layer at White Pond, USA: Supplementary Information

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SEM and EDS of microspherules and meltglass

	Volt	Acquisition Condition	Formula	mass%	Atom%	Sigma	Net	K ratio	Line
	: 20.00 kV		O	40.44	70.33	0.17	27482	0.0729505	K
		Instrument : 6510(LA)	Fe	59.56	29.67	0.34	34833	0.1184174	K
	Date : 2021/03/25	Volt : 20.00 kV	Total	100.00	100.00				
		Current : ---							

Supplementary Figure S1. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) image and energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) for a doublet spherule from WP-16-3 showing major elemental composition (Point 001).

	Volt	Acquisition Condition	Formula	mass%	Atom%	Sigma	Net	K ratio	Line
	: 20.00 kV		O	39.56	69.56	0.14	38332	0.0680298	K
		Instrument : 6510(LA)	Fe	60.44	30.44	0.29	50667	0.1151615	K
	Date : 2021/03/25	Volt : 20.00 kV	Total	100.00	100.00				
		Current : ---							

Supplementary Figure S2. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) image and energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) for a doublet spherule from WP-16-3 showing major elemental composition (Point 001).

Supplementary Figure S3. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) image for a doublet spherule from WP-16-3 showing a close-up of the region where spherules were joined during melting, including lines of deformation where one spherule impacted the other while still molten.

Volt : 20.00 kV Acquisition Condition
Mag. : x 1,200 Instrument : 6510 (LA)
Date : Volt : 20.00 kV
2021/08/05 Current : ---
Pixel : 1280 x Process Time : T4
960 Live time : 60.00
Real Time : 71.46
sec.

Formula	mass%	Atom%	Sigma	Net	K ratio	Line
O	54.52	73.02	0.05	615810	0.8573781	K
Na	0.45	0.42	0.01	9486	0.0070344	K
Al	11.13	8.84	0.03	470863	0.2104015	K
Si	16.71	12.75	0.04	668560	0.3344063	K
P	0.81	0.56	0.01	23524	0.0162242	K
K	1.32	0.72	0.01	45473	0.0351960	K
Ca	0.19	0.10	0.01	6930	0.0054413	K
Ti	1.41	0.63	0.01	35163	0.0362213	K
Cr*	0.03	0.01	0.01	585	0.0007779	K
Fe	5.16	1.98	0.02	77886	0.1388777	K
Co	nd	nd				K
Ni	nd	nd				K
Mo*	0.13	0.03	0.02	2327	0.0021974	L
Ru	nd	nd				L
Rh	nd	nd				L
Pd	nd	nd				L
W*	5.11	0.60	0.13	82147	0.0950394	M
Os*	2.17	0.25	0.09	28724	0.0298496	M
Ir	nd	nd				M
Pt*	0.86	0.09	0.05	12362	0.0127784	M
Total	100.00	100.00				

Supplementary Figure S4. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) image and energy-dispersive x-ray spectroscopy (EDS) for an aluminosilicate spherule from WP-16-3 showing major and platinum group elements (PGE) composition (Point 001).

001

Volt : 20.00 kV Acquisition Condition
 Mag. : x 1,000 Instrument : 6510(LA)
 Date : 2021/08/05 Volt : 20.00 kV
 Pixel : 1280 x Current : ---
 960 Process Time : T4
 Live time : 54.16 sec.
 Real Time : 63.92 sec.

Formula	mass%	Atom%	Sigma	Net	K ratio	Line
O	59.19	71.78	0.05	631594	0.9741724	K
Na	1.94	1.63	0.02	33993	0.0279241	K
Al	34.35	24.70	0.05	1137438	0.5630596	K
P	2.45	1.54	0.02	55294	0.0422476	K
S	0.21	0.13	0.01	5575	0.0037279	K
Cr*	0.03	0.01	0.01	375	0.0005526	K
Fe*	0.09	0.03	0.01	963	0.0019026	K
Co*	0.02	0.01	0.01	158	0.0003675	K
Ni	nd	nd				K
Mo	nd	nd				L
Ru	nd	nd				L
Rh	nd	nd				L
Pd*	0.05	0.01	0.02	729	0.0009722	L
W*	0.23	0.02	0.06	2174	0.0027858	M
Os*	0.66	0.07	0.07	6809	0.0078383	M
Ir	nd	nd				M
Pt*	0.80	0.08	0.07	9014	0.0103221	M
Total	100.00	100.00				

Supplementary Figure S5. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) image and energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) for an aluminosilicate spherule from WP-16-4 showing major and minor elemental composition (Point 001).

Volt : 20.00 kV Acquisition Condition
 Mag. : x 500 Instrument : 6510(LA)
 Date : 2021/03/16 Volt : 20.00 kV
 Pixel : 1280 x Current : ---
 960 Process Time : T4
 Live time : 51.33 sec.
 Real Time : 52.66 sec.

Formula	mass%	Atom%	Sigma	Net	K ratio	Line
O	55.27	68.87	0.13	69537	0.1131668	K
Al	19.96	14.74	0.10	95038	0.0496399	K
Si	20.41	14.49	0.12	80104	0.0468345	K
K	1.44	0.73	0.04	5287	0.0047832	K
Ca	0.89	0.44	0.03	3458	0.0031735	K
Fe	2.03	0.73	0.05	3171	0.0066097	K
Total	100.00	100.00				

Supplementary Figure S6. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) image and energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) for an aluminosilicate spherule from WP-16-3 showing major elemental composition (Point 001).

Supplementary Figure S7. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) image and energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) for an aluminosilicate spherule from WP-16-3 showing major elemental composition (Point 001).

Supplementary Figure S8. Optical and scanning electron microscopy (SEM) image for an aluminosilicate spherule from WP-16-3. See Supplementary Figures S6 and S7.

Supplementary Figure S9. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) image for a carbon spherule from WP-16-3 covered in aluminosilicate melt.

Supplementary Figure S10. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) image for a carbon spherule from WP-16-3 covered in aluminosilicate melt.

	Volt	Acquisition Condition	Formula	mass%	Atom%	Sigma	Net	K ratio	Line
	20.00 kV	Instrument : 6510 (LA)	C	40.21	49.47	0.06	20925	0.0143490	K
	Mag. : x 500	Volt : 20.00 kV	O	47.65	44.01	0.14	45271	0.1054299	K
	Date : 2021/03/16	Current : ---	Al	6.21	3.40	0.05	37914	0.0283385	K
	Pixel : 1280 x	Process Time : T4	Si	5.92	3.12	0.06	35447	0.0296578	K
	960	Live time : 35.97	Total	100.00	100.00				

Supplementary Figure S11. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) image for a carbon spherule from WP-16-3 covered in aluminosilicate melt (001).

	Volt	Acquisition Condition	Formula	mass%	Atom%	Sigma	Net	K ratio	Line
	20.00 kV	Instrument : 6510 (LA)	C	42.82	49.35	0.04	56900	0.0332843	K
	Mag. : x 500	Volt : 20.00 kV	N	16.67	16.48	0.15	3869	0.0303529	K
	Date : 2021/03/16	Current : ---	O	38.06	32.93	0.13	33797	0.0671415	K
	Pixel : 1280 x	Process Time : T4	Al	1.80	0.92	0.02	15521	0.0098860	K
	960	Live time : 42.05 sec.	Si	0.64	0.32	0.02	5839	0.0041676	K
			Total	100.00	100.00				

Supplementary Figure S12. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) image for a carbon spherule from WP-16-3 covered in aluminosilicate melt (002).

	Volt	Acquisition Condition	Formula	mass%	Atom%	Sigma	Net	K ratio	Lir
	: 20.00 kV		C	49.84	59.71	0.04	49699	0.0239372	K
Mag.	: x 500	Instrument : 6610(LA)	O	37.83	34.02	0.11	49321	0.0806751	K
Date	: 2021/03/16	Volt : 20.00 kV	Al	5.91	3.15	0.04	64155	0.0336797	K
Pixel	: 1280 x 960	Current : ---	Si	5.26	2.69	0.04	55675	0.0327170	K
		Process Time : T4	K	1.16	0.43	0.02	10413	0.0094735	K
		Live Time : 51.07 sec.	Total	100.00	100.00				
		Dead time : 59.10							

Supplementary Figure S13. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) image for a carbon spherule from WP-16-3 covered in aluminosilicate melt (004).

Supplementary Figure S14. Optical and scanning electron microscopy (SEM) image for a carbon spherule from WP-16-3 covered in aluminosilicate melt. See Supplementary Figures S9-S13.

	Volt	Acquisition Condition	Formula	mass%	Atom%	Sigma	Net	K ratio	Li
Mag.	: x 1,300	Instrument : 6510 (LA)	O	39.61	69.60	0.12	52027	0.0898898	K
Date	: 2021/03/25	Volt : 20.00 kV	Fe	60.39	30.40	0.25	68624	0.1518459	K
		Current : ---	Total	100.00	100.00				

Supplementary Figure S15. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) image and energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) for a dendritic Fe-rich spherule from WP-16-3 showing major elemental composition (Point 001).

Supplementary Figure S16. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) image for a piece of meltglass from WP-16-3.

	Volt	Mag.	Date	Pixel	Acquisition Condition	Instrument	Current	Process Time	Live time	Formula	mass%	Atom%	Sigma	Net	K ratio	Lin
	20.00 kV	x 330	2021/02/23	1280 x 960	6510 (LA)	20.00 kV	---	T4	45.23	O	48.91	64.73	0.14	47812	0.0883048	K
										Al	15.26	11.98	0.11	51451	0.0304979	K
										Si	25.90	19.53	0.16	77766	0.0515998	K
										Fe	9.92	3.76	0.11	11655	0.0275673	K
										Total	100.00	100.00				

Supplementary Figure S17. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) image and energy-dispersive x-ray spectroscopy (EDS) for a piece of meltglass from WP-16-3 showing major elemental composition (Point 001).

	Volt	Mag.	Date	Pixel	Acquisition Condition	Instrument	Current	Process Time	Live time	Real Time
	20.00 kV	x 330	2021/02/23	1280 x 960	6510 (LA)	20.00 kV	---	T4	45.23 sec.	46.41 sec.

Formula	mass%	Atom%	Sigma	Net	K ratio
C	33.44	45.32	0.06	15597	0.0084821
O	40.07	40.77	0.12	47658	0.0880210
Na	1.07	0.75	0.03	4102	0.0040350
Mg	0.44	0.29	0.02	2589	0.0015642
Al	6.80	4.10	0.05	51336	0.0304301
Si	10.43	6.04	0.06	77524	0.0514396
P	0.55	0.29	0.02	3248	0.0029716
Cl	0.37	0.17	0.02	2566	0.0022488
K	1.71	0.71	0.03	11041	0.0113369
Ca	0.33	0.14	0.02	2252	0.0023451
Ti	0.30	0.10	0.02	1322	0.0018062
Fe	4.51	1.31	0.05	11655	0.0275673
Total	100.00	100.00			

Supplementary Figure S18. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) image and energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) for a piece of meltglass from WP-16-3 showing major and minor elemental composition (Point 001).

	Volt	Acquisition Condition	Formula	mass%	Atom%	Sigma	Net	K ratio	Lin
	: 20.00 kV	Instrument : 6510(LA)	O	46.41	68.15	0.12	62541	0.0870744	K
	Mag. : x 1,700	Volt : 20.00 kV	Al	8.81	7.67	0.09	29242	0.0130666	K
	Date : 2021/02/23	Current : ---	Si	12.02	10.05	0.11	41144	0.0205797	K
	Pixel : 1280 x	Process Time : T4	K	1.92	1.15	0.05	6694	0.0051809	K
	960	Live time : 60.00 sec.	Fe	30.84	12.97	0.16	45142	0.0804916	K
			Total	100.00	100.00				

Supplementary Figure S19. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) image and energy-dispersive x-ray spectroscopy (EDS) for a section of Fe-rich crystals on meltglass from WP-16-3 showing major elemental composition (Point 001). See Supplementary Figures S16-18.

Formula	mass%	Atom%	Sigma	Net	K ratio
C	20.97	32.06	0.02	51140	0.0209661
O	41.61	47.75	0.04	407313	0.5670918
Al	18.23	12.41	0.03	892204	0.3996745
Si	7.40	4.84	0.02	309120	0.1546186
Ti*	0.27	0.10	0.01	7804	0.0020356
V*	0.03	0.01	0.01	799	0.0009287
Cr	nd	nd			
Fe	7.33	2.42	0.02	124242	0.2215342
Co	nd	nd			
Ni	nd	nd			
Mo	nd	nd			
Ru	nd	nd			
Rh	nd	nd			
Pd*	0.02	0.00	0.01	357	0.0003856
Ta	nd	nd			
W*	2.66	0.27	0.09	44714	0.0517318
Os*	1.01	0.10	0.05	16155	0.0167860
Ir*	0.16	0.02	0.03	2808	0.0028854
Pt*	0.28	0.03	0.03	4800	0.0049622
Total	100.00	100.00			

Supplementary Figure S20. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) image and energy-dispersive x-ray spectroscopy (EDS) for meltglass from WP-16-4 showing major and PGE elemental composition (Point 001).

	Volt	Acquisition Condition	Formula	mass%	Atom%	Sigma	Net	K ratio	Lin
	: 20.00 kV		C	22.20	32.68	0.02	51143	0.0209667	K
Mag.	: x 120	Instrument : 6510(LA)	O	42.76	47.26	0.04	407385	0.5671923	K
Date	: 2021/08/05	Volt : 20.00 kV	Al	19.10	12.51	0.03	891291	0.3982661	K
Pixel	: 1280 x 960	Current : ---	Si	7.92	4.99	0.03	311411	0.1557643	K
		Process Time : T4	Ti	0.29	0.11	0.01	7913	0.0081509	K
		Live time : 60.00 sec.	Fe	7.74	2.45	0.03	124242	0.2215350	K
		Real Time : 69.39 sec.	Total	100.00	100.00				

Supplementary Figure S21. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) image and energy-dispersive x-ray spectroscopy (EDS) for meltglass from WP-16-4 showing major elemental composition (Point 001).

Formula	mass%	Atom%	Sigma	Net	K ratio	Line
C	23.92	45.80	0.03	42531	0.0278380	K
O	17.55	25.23	0.05	107082	0.2380334	K
Al	9.18	7.83	0.03	207332	0.1479162	K
Si	3.08	2.52	0.03	72223	0.0576771	K
V*	0.02	0.01	0.01	331	0.0006152	K
Cr*	0.02	0.01	0.01	358	0.0007601	K
Fe	44.62	18.37	0.07	474344	1.3503963	K
Co	nd	nd				K
Ni*	0.07	0.03	0.02	484	0.0019361	K
Mo*	0.04	0.01	0.03	543	0.0008192	L
Ru*	0.04	0.01	0.02	647	0.0009263	L
Rh*	0.10	0.02	0.02	1633	0.0024016	L
Pd	nd	nd				L
Hf*	0.34	0.04	0.10	2719	0.0053305	M
Ta	nd	nd				M
W*	0.70	0.09	0.10	6642	0.0122690	M
Os*	0.08	0.01	0.06	789	0.0013093	M
Ir*	0.22	0.03	0.05	2381	0.0038778	M
Pt	nd	nd				M
Total	100.00	100.00				

JEOL EDS System

JEOL

Supplementary Figure S22. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) image and energy-dispersive x-ray spectroscopy (EDS) for an inclusion of low-oxygen Fe embedded in meltglass from WP-16-4 showing major elemental composition (Point 001).

Bayesian age-depth model

Supplementary Figure S23. Bayesian age-depth model for White Pond (WP-2016-3) showing core lithology for the lowermost portion of core 2016-3, depths for stratigraphic units, a Bayesian age/depth model based on 22 AMS dates, platinum (Pt) abundance (error = ± 0.1 ppb), Bayesian modeled age range for the YD onset (12,835–12,735 cal yr BP at 95% Confidence Interval using IntCal13; 12,875–12,775 cal BP using IntCal20) based on Kennett *et al.*¹ is shown as a light-yellow zone (~ 211.5 -224 cm) within stratigraphic Unit II. The YDB spore minimum for Strongly Coprophilous spores is Bayesian modeled at $12,752 \pm 54$ cal. BP, platinum peak at $12,785 \pm 58$ cal BP, and soot peak at $12,838 \pm 103$ cal BP. Data sets used in this figure come from duplicate cores that are correlated using lithostratigraphic Unit II as a common core datum. Dates used in this figure are from Moore *et al.*². This Figure is adapted from Moore *et al.*².

Supplementary Figure S24. Comparative ranges of elemental ratios for nanoparticles from the Younger Dryas Boundary (YDB) at White Pond relative to terrestrial and extraterrestrial materials. Panels show logarithmic ranges for the ratios (a) Pt/Fe, (b) Ir/Fe, and (c) HSE/Ni, where HSE represents the highly siderophile elements, Au, Ir, Os, Pd, and Pt. Green bars represent ratios measured for nanoparticles from the YDB interval at White Pond determined by SP-ICP-TOF-MS. Comparative fields include comets, refractory metal nuggets, micrometeorites, iron meteorites, chondrites, achondrites, ureilites, interplanetary dust particles (IDPs), magmatic rocks, and upper continental crust. Upper continental crust values are shown with an estimated uncertainty of ± 0.5 log units. Nanoparticles represent a trace component of the sediment and are not representative of bulk sediment chemistry. The YDB nanoparticle ratios overlap strongly with metal-rich and refractory extraterrestrial components and show no overlap with crustal values or magmatic compositions, potentially consistent with a non-volcanic and non-terrestrial origin.

Supporting Information Text.

S1. Data sources, comparative materials, and caveats for nanoparticle ratio plots. The comparative ratio plots shown in Figure X (main manuscript) and Supplementary Figure SX were constructed to place Younger Dryas Boundary (YDB) nanoparticles from White Pond into a broader geochemical context relative to terrestrial and extraterrestrial materials. This section summarizes the data sources, assumptions, and limitations underlying those comparisons, and clarifies how the plotted ranges should be interpreted.

Crustal reference values represent upper continental crust compositions compiled primarily from Rudnick and Gao and related syntheses, plotted with an estimated uncertainty envelope of ± 0.5 log units to reflect natural lithologic variability, analytical uncertainty, and compilation differences among datasets. These values are intended as first-order reference ranges rather than precise compositional limits and are used to distinguish crustal background from anomalous enrichments.

The category “metal nuggets” refers specifically to refractory metal nuggets, which are micron- to submicron-scale metal alloy particles commonly reported in carbonaceous chondrites, cometary dust, interplanetary dust particles (IDPs), and micrometeorites. These particles are characteristically enriched in platinum-group elements (PGEs) relative to bulk host materials and are widely interpreted as high-temperature condensates formed in the early solar nebula or during subsequent thermal processing. As such, they represent a physically and geochemically distinct carrier phase rather than a bulk lithologic component.

Comparative ranges for meteorites (including iron meteorites, chondrites, achondrites, and ureilites) and magmatic rocks were compiled primarily from Moore et al. (2017)² and the GERM Database (<https://earthref.org/GERM/D/>; accessed 2026). These datasets integrate measurements obtained using multiple analytical techniques, including bulk ICP-MS, electron microprobe, LA-ICP-MS, SIMS, and SEM-EDS. Consequently, the plotted fields represent order-of-magnitude envelopes capturing typical variability within each material class rather than exhaustive or extreme bounds.

Cometary data include measurements from Comet Wild 2 samples returned by the Stardust mission, as well as analyses of giant cometary particles (GCPs). Sources include published datasets from Stephan (2010)³, Joswiak et al. (2017)⁴, Leitner et al. (2008)³, Brownlee et al. (2006, 2008)^{5,6}, Flynn et al. (2006)⁷, Ishii et al. (2008)⁸, and Gainsforth et al. (2020)⁹. These datasets are considered representative but not exhaustive. In addition, it is important to note that cometary nuclei are not rocks but loosely consolidated aggregates of ice, dust, and refractory grains, with porosities commonly estimated at ~60–80%. This structural and compositional heterogeneity complicates direct comparison with lithified terrestrial materials and motivates the use of broad, conservative ratio ranges.

Nanoparticles from White Pond represent a trace subset of the sediment and are not representative of bulk sediment chemistry. Nanoparticles are detected throughout the sediment column at low background levels, reflecting continuous background deposition of cosmic dust (“cosmic rain”) and the high mobility of nanoparticles within sediment pore waters. The YDB interval is distinguished by nanoparticle concentrations approximately an order of magnitude greater than background levels, defining an anomalous and stratigraphically confined enrichment relative to surrounding sediments.

The White Pond nanoparticles were measured by SP-ICP-TOF-MS, whereas most comparative datasets were generated using other analytical techniques. As a result, the comparisons emphasize relative positioning, order-of-magnitude overlap, and exclusion of major

source categories rather than strict one-to-one equivalence of analytical precision or detection limits. The plotted ranges should therefore be interpreted as conservative envelopes designed to test source compatibility rather than as exact compositional matches.

The number of datapoints contributing to each ratio field differs substantially among material classes. For the YDB nanoparticles, sample counts are Ir/Fe ($n = 24$), Pt/Fe ($n = 16$), and Ni/Fe ($n = 40$), whereas comparative datasets typically include hundreds to more than a thousand individual measurements, depending on material class. Despite these differences, consistent patterns emerge across all three ratios: (1) strong overlap between YDB nanoparticles and metal-rich extraterrestrial components (comets, refractory metal nuggets, micrometeorites, and iron meteorites), (2) little to no overlap with magmatic compositions, and (3) limited or no overlap with most silicate meteorite groups for Pt/Fe and Ir/Fe.

Importantly, the plotted ranges are intentionally conservative and do not represent extreme values within any material class. In several cases, published datasets extend beyond the plotted envelopes; however, widening the ranges to include rare end-members would not alter the primary interpretation. The key result is the relative position of the YDB nanoparticle ratios within metal-rich extraterrestrial fields and their clear separation from crustal and magmatic compositions.

Together, these considerations indicate that the comparative ratio plots are robust at the level of interpretation used in the main manuscript and provide meaningful constraints on the origin and likely carrier phases of YDB nanoparticles at White Pond.

Supplementary Tables

Supplementary Table S1. White Pond AMS dates including those used in the Bayesian age-depth model in Moore et al.². Table Adapted from Moore et al. (2019)².

Depth (cm) ^a	Sample interval ^b	Core ^c	Uncalibrated age	Calibrated age (cal BP)			Material dated ^e	Lab number ^f	
			(¹⁴ C yr BP)	μ	σ	(2 sigma range) ^d			
162	+46 to +48	WP-2016-2	8580 +/- 30	9540	25	9600	9485	seed	Beta-470437
164	+44 to +46	WP-2016-3	8940 +/- 30	10,070	90	10,205	9910	Alkali Insoluble Organics	Beta-499322
165	+43.3 to +42.3	WP-2015	6070 +/- 30	6925	60	7150	6795	charcoal	Beta-412233
170	+38 to +40	WP-2016-2	8720 +/- 30	9665	75	9890	9545	seed	Beta-470436
177	+32 to +34	WP-2016-3	9000 +/- 30	10,185	60	10,240	9965	seed	Beta-469117
179	+30 to +32	WP-2016-3	9375 +/- 25	10,600	50	10,685	10,505	seed	UCI-190027
188	+21.8 to +22.8	WP-2015	7950 +/- 30	8815	100	8985	8645	seed	Beta-430153
189.5	+20 to +22	WP-2016-3	8810 +/- 30	9855	110	10120	9685	seed	Beta-470900
193.5	+16 to +18	WP-2016-3	7520 +/- 20	8340	40	8390	8215	seed	UCI-190028
193.5 (dup)	+16 to +18 (dup)	WP-2016-3	8950 +/- 30	10085	90	10215	9910	Alkali Insoluble Organics	Beta-480583
198	+12 to +14	WP-2016-3	7950 +/- 25	8820	100	8985	8645	seed	UCI-190029
198 (dup)	+12 to +14 (dup)	WP-2016-3	9170 +/- 30	10,325	60	10,485	10,240	Alkali Insoluble Organics	Beta-480582
200.2	+10 to +12	WP-2016-3	9040 +/- 30	10,215	20	10,245	10,180	Alkali Insoluble Organics	Beta-502745
204	+6 to +8	WP-2016-3	9985 +/- 30	11,450	105	11,685	11,270	seed	UCI-190030
206.4	+4 to +6	WP-2016-3	9210 +/- 30	10,365	65	10,495	10,250	Alkali Insoluble Organics	Beta-502744
210	+1.1 to +2.1	WP-2015	10,860 +/- 40	12,785	35	12,840	12,730	seed	Beta-415415
210.5	0 to +2	WP-2016-3	8870 +/- 30	10,010	95	10,170	9,790	seed	Beta-470901
210.5 (dup)	0 to +2 (dup)	WP-2016-3	9230 +/- 30	10,390	70	10,505	10,260	Alkali Insoluble Organics	Beta-499326
212.5	0.6 to -1.6	WP-2015	10,970 +/- 30	12,875	55	12,990	12,760	seed	Beta-414623
212.5	0 to -2	WP-2016-3	10,900 +/- 30	12,800	30	12,885	12,750	seed	Beta-450657
212.5	0 to -2	WP-2016-4	10,930 +/- 25	12,820	40	12,895	12,755	plant macrofossil	UCI-250415 ^g
219	-6 to -8	WP-2016-3	11,010 +/- 40	12,940	70	13,080	12,830	seed	Beta-453269
219.5	-6.8 to -7.8	WP-2015	11,320 +/- 40	13,210	45	13,305	13,115	seed	Beta-430154
221	-8 to -10	WP-2016-3	10,640 +/- 30	12,670	40	12,725	12,615	plant macrofossils	Beta-450658
223.5	-12 to -14	WP-2016-1	10,920 +/- 40	12,820	45	12,905	12,750	seed	Beta-502827
223	-10 to -12	WP-2016-3	11,170 +/- 40	13,100	40	13,170	12,995	seed	Beta-453270
225	-12.2 to 13.6	WP-2015	11,470 +/- 40	13,350	55	13,455	13,240	seed	Beta-412234
229.5	-16 to -18	WP-2016-3	11,285 +/- 30	13,170	40	13,245	13,100	seed	UCI-190031
253	-38 to -40	WP-2016-3	12,330 +/- 40	14,385	210	14,820	14,105	seed	Beta-470902
261	-46 to -48	WP-2016-3	Modern	--	--	--	--	seed	UCI-190032
263	-48.6 to 47.6	WP-2015	12,920 +/- 50	15,445	95	15,625	15,270	plant macrofossil	Beta-412235

^aCore depth for all samples referenced to depths for WP-2016-3 based on lithology.

^bDue to differential depths for core lithologies between cores, the relative depth for AMS samples is based on using the peat to mud transition (top of Unit II) common to all cores as a datum with samples indexed as above (+) or below (-) this transition.

^cOnly dates from 2016 cores were used to construct the Bayesian age/depth model.

^d2-Sigma calibrated age ranges derived from INTCAL20.

^eMaterials dated include aquatic seeds, plant fragments, and charcoal recovered from core samples and bulk dating of peat using the Alkali Insoluble fraction.

^fBeta Analytic, Inc and UCIAMS (Keck Carbon Cycle AMS Lab, University of California, Irvine).

^gRecent AMS date from WP-2016-4 not included in Moore et al. 2019 paper.

Supplementary Table S2. Microspherule and meltglass abundance.

^a Sample Depth (cm)	Depth (midpoint)	Sample Weight (g)	Meltglass	^b Meltglass/kg	Spherules	^b Spherules/kg
85-87	86	15	0	0	0	0
105-107	106	15	0	0	0	0
113-115	114	15	0	0	0	0
115-117	116	15	0	0	0	0
117-119	118	15	0	0	0	0
119-121	120	15	1	67	6	400
121-123	122	15	1	67	2	130
123-125	124	15	0	0	0	0
125-127	126	15	0	0	0	0
135-137	136	15	0	0	0	0
177-179	178	15	0	0	0	0

^aDepths are for core WP-16-4.

^bAbundance estimates are extrapolated based on sample size used for analysis.

Supplementary Table S3. Operating conditions for inductively coupled plasma-time of flight-mass spectrometer analysis (TOFWERK icpTOF R).

Instrument parameter	Value				
Plasma Power	1550 V				
Nebulizer Gas Flow	1.1-1.14 L/min				
Auxiliary Gas Flow	0.8 L/min				
Cooling Gas Flow	14 L/min				
Injector Diameter	2.5 mm				
Collision Cell Gas	5 mL/min He with 4.5% H ₂				
CCT Bias	-2.50 V				
Notch	Mass	29	32	36.3	41
	Amplitude (V)	1.6	2.0	2.0	1.2
Data acquisition	Continuous Mode				
Detected Mass Range	14-275 m/Z				
TOF Repetition Rate	33 kHz				
TOF Time Resolution	30 μ s				
Integration Time	2 ms				
Sample Flow Rate	0.455 mL/min				
Transport Efficiency	6.6%				
(CeO/Ce)	< 3.0%				

Supplementary Table S4 Elements were monitored for single particle-inductively coupled plasma-time of flight-mass spectrometer analysis and the corresponding particle mass and size detection limits.

Element	Isotope	Mass detection limit (g)	Size detection limit (nm, assuming pure metallic particle)	Size detection limit (nm, assuming pure metal oxide particle)	Metal oxide form
Al	²⁷ Al	6.90×10^{-15}	170	185	Al ₂ O ₃
Ti	⁴⁸ Ti	7.19×10^{-16}	67	82	TiO ₂
V	⁵¹ V	4.20×10^{-16}	51	75	V ₂ O ₅
Cr	⁵² Cr	3.27×10^{-16}	44	56	Cr ₂ O ₃
Mn	⁵⁵ Mn	2.48×10^{-16}	40	53	MnO ₂
Fe	⁵⁶ Fe	8.88×10^{-16}	60	77	Fe ₂ O ₃
Co	⁵⁹ Co	1.99×10^{-16}	35	44	Co ₃ O ₄
Ni	⁶⁰ Ni	8.64×10^{-16}	57	68	NiO
Cu	⁶⁵ Cu	6.66×10^{-16}	52	63	CuO
Zn	⁶⁶ Zn	1.50×10^{-15}	74	86	ZnO
As	⁷⁵ As	1.55×10^{-15}	80	101	As ₂ O ₃
Zr	⁹⁰ Zr	3.29×10^{-16}	46	53	ZrO ₂

Nb	⁹³ Nb	1.56×10^{-16}	33	44	Nb ₂ O ₅
Ru	¹⁰² Ru	4.16×10^{-16}	48	53	RuO ₂
Rh	¹⁰³ Rh	9.51×10^{-17}	30	35	Rh ₂ O ₃
Pd	¹⁰⁶ Pd	5.45×10^{-16}	67	59	PdO
Sn	¹²⁰ Sn	3.25×10^{-16}	44	48	SnO ₂
Sb	¹²¹ Sb	2.61×10^{-16}	42	49	Sb ₂ O ₃
Ba	¹³⁸ Ba	9.50×10^{-17}	37	33	BaO
La	¹³⁹ La	7.29×10^{-17}	28	29	La ₂ O ₃
Ce	¹⁴⁰ Ce	8.63×10^{-17}	29	30	CeO ₂
Pr	¹⁴¹ Pr	6.23×10^{-17}	26	28	Pr ₆ O ₁₁
Nd	¹⁴² Nd	1.70×10^{-16}	36	37	Nd ₂ O ₃
Sm	¹⁵² Sm	2.07×10^{-16}	38	38	Sm ₂ O ₃
Eu	¹⁵³ Eu	1.00×10^{-16}	33	31	Eu ₂ O ₃
Gd	¹⁵⁸ Gd	2.39×10^{-16}	39	41	Gd ₂ O ₃
Tb	¹⁵⁹ Tb	5.26×10^{-17}	23	25	Tb ₄ O ₇
Dy	¹⁶⁴ Dy	1.72×10^{-16}	34	36	Dy ₂ O ₃
Ho	¹⁶⁵ Ho	5.10×10^{-17}	22	24	Ho ₂ O ₃
Er	¹⁶⁶ Er	1.53×10^{-16}	32	34	Er ₂ O ₃
Tm	¹⁶⁹ Tm	5.15×10^{-17}	22	24	Tm ₂ O ₃
Yb	¹⁷⁴ Yb	1.57×10^{-16}	36	33	Yb ₂ O ₃
Lu	¹⁷⁵ Lu	4.38×10^{-17}	20	22	Lu ₂ O ₃
Hf	¹⁸⁰ Hf	1.95×10^{-16}	30	36	HfO ₂
Ta	¹⁸¹ Ta	1.78×10^{-16}	33	42	Ta ₂ O ₅
W	¹⁸⁴ W	3.55×10^{-16}	27	37	WO ₂
Re	¹⁸⁷ Re	1.04×10^{-16}	26	29	ReO ₂
Os	¹⁹² Os	1.20×10^{-16}	27	30	OsO ₂
Ir	¹⁹³ Ir	1.54×10^{-16}	25	32	IrO ₂
Pt	¹⁹⁵ Pt	4.09×10^{-16}	41	45	PtO ₂
Au	¹⁹⁷ Au	2.09×10^{-16}	28	34	Au ₂ O ₃
Pb	²⁰⁸ Pb	1.19×10^{-16}	27	30	PbO
Th	²³² Th	7.64×10^{-17}	23	26	ThO ₂
U	²³⁸ U	6.82×10^{-17}	19	24	UO ₂

The particle mass detection limit is calculated according to the Poisson distribution =

$$Mass_{detection\ limit} = 3.29\sqrt{background\ signal} + 2.71$$

The size detection limit is calculated as the equivalent spherical diameter from the particle mass detection limit, assuming pure metal and metal oxide phases.

Supplementary Table S5. USGS Reference material BIR-1G data and detection limits.

	units	BIR1-G average			Reference values	% deviation	Detection limits
		(n=7)	STDEV	RSD	(GEOREM)	from Lit	
Na2O wt%	wt%	1.9	0.06	3%	1.85	1%	0.0916
MgO wt%	wt%	9.7	0.43	4%	9.4	3%	0.0160
Al2O3 wt%	wt%	14.5	0.22	2%	15.5	-7%	0.0223
SiO2 wt%	wt%	48.3	0.56	1%	47.5	2%	7.7405
CaO wt%	wt%	12.1	0.56	5%	13.3	-9%	0.2339
Sc	ppm	39.0	0.62	2%	43	-9%	1.5966
TiO2 wt%	wt%	0.9	0.03	3%	1.04	-13%	0.0039
V	ppm	317.4	6.57	2%	326	-3%	0.6232
Cr	ppm	445.1	20.34	5%	392	14%	13.5434
MnO wt%	wt%	0.2	0.01	4%	0.19	-15%	0.0122
FeO wt%	wt%	10.4	0.24	2%	10.4	0%	0.0156
Co	ppm	53.0	1.99	4%	52	2%	0.6268
Ni	ppm	197.1	7.06	4%	178	11%	8.7188
Cu	ppm	144.6	6.52	5%	119	21%	0.9511
Zn	ppm	68.9	2.06	3%	78	-12%	3.4550
Rb	ppm	0.3	0.05	17%	0.197	33%	0.1189
Sr	ppm	107.4	3.90	4%	109	-1%	0.2367
Y	ppm	13.0	0.45	3%	14.3	-9%	0.0287
Zr	ppm	12.3	0.12	1%	14	-12%	1.7960
Nb	ppm	0.5	0.02	4%	0.52	-1%	0.0049
Mo	ppm	0.103	0.02	22%	0.075	37%	0.0402
Rh	ppm	0.005	0.00	77%	not reported		0.0036
Pd	ppm	0.060	0.03	45%	not reported		0.0458
Ba	ppm	6.608	0.15	2%	6.5	2%	1.2978
La	ppm	0.575	0.02	4%	0.609	-6%	0.0013
Ce	ppm	1.928	0.04	2%	1.89	2%	0.0012
Nd	ppm	2.259	0.10	5%	2.37	-5%	0.0061
Sm	ppm	1.061	0.10	9%	1.09	-3%	0.0406
Gd	ppm	1.632	0.07	4%	1.85	-12%	0.1237
Dy	ppm	2.232	0.08	4%	2.55	-12%	0.0031
Er	ppm	1.523	0.08	5%	1.7	-10%	0.0033
Yb	ppm	1.462	0.06	4%	1.64	-11%	0.0095
Hf	ppm	0.472	0.06	13%	0.57	-17%	0.0044
Re	ppm	0.001	0.00	77%	0.00053	143%	0.0007
Ir	ppm	0.006	0.00	76%	not reported		0.0018
Pt	ppm	0.904	0.07	7%	0.92	-2%	0.0022
Pb	ppm	3.655	0.23	6%	3.7	-1%	0.0159
Th	ppm	0.026	0.00	15%	0.03	-14%	0.0002
U	ppm	0.018	0.00	16%	0.023	-21%	0.0001

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